

A Framework for 3D Modeling of Construction Sites Using Aerial Imagery and Semantic NeRFs

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Abstract. The rapid evolution of drone technology has revolutionized data acquisition in the construction industry, offering a cost-effective and efficient method to monitor and map engineering structures. However, a significant challenge remains in transforming the drone-collected data into semantically meaningful 3D models. 3D reconstruction techniques usually lead to raw point clouds that are typically unstructured and lack the semantic and geometric information of objects needed for civil engineering tools. Our solution applies semantic segmentation algorithms to the data produced by NeRF (Neural Radiance Fields), effectively transforming drone-captured 3D volumetric representations into semantically rich 3D models. This approach offers a cost-effective and automated way to digitalize physical objects of construction sites into semantically annotated digital counterparts facilitating the development of digital twins or XR applications in the construction sector.

Keywords: Neural Radiance Fields · Digital Twins · Drone Technology · 3D Modeling · Digitalization in Construction

1 Introduction

In the construction industry, efficient management is crucial and relies heavily on precise 3D representations of project sites. Traditional methods of acquiring data for these representations often involve expensive hardware and time-consuming tasks, a gap filled by the high-resolution data provided by drone technology and the emerging capabilities of computer vision. Drones have been used in various industries, including agriculture, public safety, and military purposes, and have recently been introduced to the construction industry [2]. They provide invaluable help and cost savings with wide views of inaccessible and otherwise difficult and tough to navigate locations, facilitating aerial surveying of buildings, bridges, roads, and highways, and ultimately saving project time and costs [2, 19, 23]. Digital twins and XR applications can benefit from computer vision to enable construction progress monitoring, safety inspection, and quality management [12, 15]. However, challenges exist in the analysis process. Transforming drone-collected visual data into semantically meaningful 3D models remains a challenge. Recent implicit neural reconstruction techniques, such

as Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) [21], are appealing as they rapidly generate 3D representations, but these are not directly usable for civil engineering tools, digital twins, or XR applications as they do not include semantic labels.

Semantic scene understanding involves attaching class labels to a geometric model. The tasks of estimating the geometric model from images can benefit from the smoothness, coherence, and self-similarity learned by self-supervision methods [38]. Scene consistency is inherent to the training process and enables the network to produce accurate geometry of the scene. However, unlike scene geometry, semantic classes are human-defined concepts, and it is not possible to semantically label a novel scene in a purely self-supervised manner. Moreover, the majority of existing works pursue offline, passive analysis, in which scene understanding is conducted over already acquired sequences of data [37]. Regrettably, this approach often significantly restricts the effectiveness of scene understanding, as data collection is separate from the corresponding scene understanding algorithms. Moreover, the absence of extensive labeled 3D training datasets, like those available for 2D images (ImageNet, COCO, etc), prevents 3D methods from benefiting from pre-training on large-scale 2D datasets.

In this paper, we propose an innovative application that leverages NeRF for generating 3D representations from drone data. Specifically, we develop an end-to-end pipeline that combines the benefits of UAV-based data capture, semantic segmentation, and NeRF’s continuous scene representation capabilities to transform raw drone footage into semantically-rich 3D models of construction sites. Our key technical contributions include an automated UAV footage collection methodology tailored for construction sites that generates images from multiple viewpoints to enable accurate 3D reconstruction. A data preprocessing stage extracts frames, annotates them using semantic segmentation to identify construction objects, and estimates camera poses. We train a custom Semantic-NeRF model that takes the UAV images, semantic labels of classes of interest, and poses as input to jointly learn the scene’s appearance, geometry, and semantics. Marching cubes algorithm is used to extract the final 3D model labeled with semantic classes from the trained model. Compared to existing techniques that produce unstructured point clouds lacking semantics, our approach generates textured 3D models, addressing a key gap in digitizing as-built construction sites. We demonstrate our pipeline on a real highway bridge construction project. The ability to automatically create an as-built 3D model from only drone video footage can enable powerful digital twinning and immersive applications for construction industry.

2 Background: The Intersection of NeRF, Semantic Segmentation, and UAV Technology

The integration of advanced computational techniques with UAV technology has led to significant advancements in 3D modeling and monitoring of construction projects. This section provides a comprehensive review of three key components of our proposed end-to-end pipeline for 3D construction site modeling: Neural

Radiance Fields (NeRF), Semantic Analysis, and UAV Technology. We explore the foundational knowledge and related works in each area, highlighting their intersection and potential for enhancing construction site modeling.

In recent years, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), also known as drones, have revolutionized data acquisition in various fields, such as agriculture [30], disaster management [1], environmental monitoring [10], extending even to military applications [32] and construction project monitoring [3, 18]. Over the past few years, the construction sector has notably evolved, driven by technological advancements. The integration of UAVs as a pioneering technological advancement, holds the promise to boost various construction activities. These enhancements include tasks ranging from observation and inspection to the monitoring of safety practices, resulting in significant savings in terms of time, expenditures, and the mitigation of injuries. Furthermore, it augments the overall quality of work performed. UAVs have transformed the project planning, execution and maintenance in the construction industry. Their agility and accessibility to capture high-resolution images and navigate challenging surfaces makes them ideal platforms for collecting visual data. Several studies have explored the use of UAVs for construction site monitoring and 3D modeling. For instance, Anwar et al. [2] utilized UAVs to capture aerial images for monitoring and progress assessment of construction projects. By leveraging UAV technology, construction tasks can benefit from efficient and cost-effective data collection, enabling real-time monitoring and analysis, 3D modeling and remote inspections with remarkable precision.

Creating realistic renderings of real-world scenes from various viewpoints using traditional computer vision techniques is a complex task, as it involves capturing detailed models of appearance and geometry. However, recent research has shown encouraging progress by employing learning-based approaches that can implicitly encode both geometry and appearance without relying on explicit 3D supervision. These studies have demonstrated promising outcomes in generating photo-realistic renderings with the freedom to view scenes from different angles. Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) [21] have emerged as a powerful technique for scene reconstruction and rendering, revolutionizing the field of computer vision. Particularly it is a state-of-the-art technique for scene reconstruction that models volumetric scenes as continuous functions, enabling the synthesis of novel views and realistic rendering [34]. In simple terms, NeRF demonstrates its capability to reconstruct complex 3D scenes from 2D images. Since its inception, and given its results, it has witnessed significant progress and inspired numerous extensions and variations. For instance, Zhang et al. [35] introduced improvements to the original NeRF formulation, enhancing its efficiency and robustness. Martin-Brualla et al. [20] extended NeRF to handle unstructured and diverse real-world scenes, enabling reconstruction from internet photo collections. Also, Barron et al. [4] in their approach mitigated undesirable aliasing artifacts and greatly enhanced the NeRF model’s capacity to capture intricate details.

Semantic segmentation [22], a fundamental task in computer vision and machine learning, plays a crucial role in understanding and extracting meaningful

information from images by classifying each pixel into specific semantic categories. Before the rise of deep learning methods, traditional approaches heavily relied on handcrafted feature extraction and classification design such as K-means algorithm, support vector machines, and decision trees. In recent years, deep neural networks have achieved great performances in semantic segmentation tasks [36, 7, 31] which provide valuable insights for incorporating contextual information into the 3D modeling process. Semantically annotated point clouds, which constitute a crucial geometric data structure, have attracted numerous researchers. In contrast to two-dimensional data, their sparsity and randomness make them full of challenges. Some of the most common challenges are the scale of the data and the lack of clear structures. However, Landrieu et al. [17] proposed a deep learning-based method for semantic segmentation in large scale point clouds. Also, Hu et al. [13] designed an efficient neural architecture to directly infer per-point semantics for large-scale point clouds, in a single pass, significantly reducing computational cost and memory requirements. Furthermore, Qi et al. [24] designed a deep network architecture that directly consumes point clouds for semantic segmentation in order to minimize data corruption which may be caused by transforming data prior feed them to the network, as traditional methods apply. Later, as an extension of the previous work, a hierarchical neural network architecture was designed [25] to efficiently capture both local and global features from point clouds, enhancing the accuracy of point-wise semantic segmentation.

Integration of semantic segmentation with the Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) has gained attention due to its potential to enhance scene reconstruction and rendering. Several studies have explored the combination of these two techniques, highlighting their complementary nature and the benefits they offer. One line of research has focused on leveraging semantic segmentation to improve the quality and accuracy of 3D reconstructions with NeRFs. For instance, Fu et al.[11] unified coarse 3D annotations with 2D semantic cues transferred from existing datasets, utilizing NeRF. With this combination both semantic and geometry are optimized. However, this method requires a priori knowledge of 3D objects and their boundary boxes for improvement. By incorporating semantic information, the aim is to guide the reconstruction process and achieve more meaningful and semantically consistent 3D models [14]. Towards this direction, Zhi et al.[38] enhanced NeRF’s robust 3D representations with sparse or noisy annotations to produce a scene-specific 3D semantic representation. This work had the biggest influence on the development of our proposal pipeline. In the same direction, Kundu et al. [16] preprocessed 2D images to extract 2D semantic segmentations and camera parameters. Additionally he utilized jointly a set of 3D oriented bounding boxes and category labels to optimize the extracted results. Another direction in the literature has explored the use of NeRF for refining and enhancing semantic segmentation results. By leveraging the continuous scene representation offered by NeRF, researchers strove to improve the precision and robustness of semantic segmentation [33]. In the context of con-

struction site modeling [5], semantic segmentation enables the identification and segmentation of various objects and structures.

3 Methodology: Building a Pipeline for Semantic NeRF Analysis of UAV Footage

In this section the deployed end-to-end framework for 3D modeling of construction sites is presented. As illustrated in Figure 1, the proposed pipeline consists of three distinct stages, each of which will be thoroughly explained in the subsequent sections.

Fig. 1: Illustration of the proposed pipeline for 3D modeling of a construction site. The process includes three main stages: UAV data acquisition (Stage 1), data preprocessing to create a scene-specific dataset (Stage 2) and reconstruction of the semantic 3D model via Semantic-NeRF (Stage 3).

3.1 UAV Technology and Data Acquisition

In the first stage, data acquisition in the designated target area is conducted. For this purpose, a UAV equipped with a high resolution camera is utilized to capture footage from the scene. UAV utilization enables a seamless process of data collection, as it can access otherwise inaccessible areas and capture the target region from multiple perspectives, while minimizing human effort. The main objective is to create a meaningful dataset, containing images from varying viewing angles of the examined scene, that will allow accurate 3D reconstruction. To this end, the UAV path is carefully designed to scan the whole area and capture the existing essential instances in detail, from diverse distances and heights relative to the target. The UAV speed is also adjusted accordingly, aiming to minimize any distortion or blurring effects and receive high resolution visual data. In this manner, sufficient overlap of imagery is ensured, resulting in a dataset that is usable for 3D reconstruction.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

In Stage 2, data preprocessing is performed to prepare the required dataset for the semantic 3D reconstruction, containing RGB images, the corresponding se-

mantic labels and the estimated camera poses. The collected footage is processed accordingly through 3 steps. At first, RGB frames from the captured footage are extracted. Sampling frequency for frame extraction is defined accordingly to ensure the required amount of overlap among the extracted consecutive frames. Next, the labeling of the RGB images is conducted in an automated manner, aiming to avoid the time-consuming and laborious manual labeling. To achieve that, a deep learning-based method that semantically annotates construction-related classes is deployed. In specific, the robust DeepLabv3+ [8] architecture pre-trained on ADE20K [39] dataset is employed, enabling the accurate pixel-wise annotation of the RGB images. Following this, camera poses calculation is conducted, determining the position and the orientation of the camera in 3D space for each image. To achieve that, Structure from Motion (SfM) [28] process is followed. The typical process initially requires extracting features per image to identify distinctive points in the 2D image plane. Then, feature matching is applied, to recognize the spatial correspondences between the images. In this context, two pretrained deep-learning models are utilized, namely SuperPoint [9] and SuperGlue [27] for feature extraction and feature matching, respectively. The employment of these models provides accurate results and a balanced trade-off with regard to computational time. Next, the position of the acquired features in 3D space is calculated, following the triangulation method. Last, camera poses iteratively estimated through an optimization process, guaranteeing the alignment between the observed 2D features and their corresponding 3D position. For the aforementioned process, the pinhole camera model is adapted.

3.3 Semantic NeRF Implementation

The final stage of the presented pipeline involves the utilization of the deployed dataset in order to train a Semantic-NeRF instance and acquire a 3D reconstruction of the scene. Contrary to NeRF-based models, Semantic-NeRF is capable of generating 3D representations enriched with semantic information from the input data.

In specific, the custom-built dataset contains the UAV captured RGB images, the corresponding semantic labels and the camera poses. This dataset is utilized to train the deployed Semantic-NeRF from scratch. Through the training process, the model learns to predict the radiance (color and density) and the semantic class for a given point and view direction in the 3D space. Upon completion of training, the 3D representation of the scene can be extracted. To this end, 3D grids of the scene are passed to the trained model to acquire the network predictions. Next, the marching cubes algorithm is applied to extract the geometric meshes. The final output is a detailed 3D model of the construction scene, where depicted instances are semantically annotated. This semantic 3D reconstruction provides a comprehensive overview of the examined area, enabling its exploitation for various construction-related operations and applications.

Fig. 2: General view of the examined highway overpass construction site[6].

4 Experimental Configurations and Results

In this section, the deployment of the proposed end-to-end pipeline to a specific construction site is presented. More specifically, the developed framework was tested over a highway overpass located in the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona (see Fig 2), aiming to create the semantic 3D representation of one of the bridge pillars. The overall length of the bridge is estimated at approximately 846 meters, connecting two of the main highways of the city’s network, crossing over rivers, roads and railway lines. Given this information, using hand-held LiDAR devices to obtain 3D representations would significantly escalate both the cost and the time required for scanning, presenting substantial challenge in terms of resources and efficiency. In our case, acquiring the 3D model of each pillar in an automated way is considered of crucial importance to enable efficient monitoring of the infrastructure.

Based on the developed framework, data collection was conducted as outlined in Stage 1, with the use of a DJI Mavic Pro UAV model. Its trajectory was designed accordingly to cover the target object from varying viewing points and distances. Toward this direction, the examined bridge pillar was captured during the UAV mission, leading to a high-resolution video of the scene. An illustration of the executed UAV path is presented in Figure 5b. The acquired footage had a duration of 4 minutes and 50 seconds (4:50 min), with a resolution of 3840×2160 pixels and recorded at a frame rate of 30 frames per second (fps). In order to compose the required dataset to build the semantic 3D model, data preprocessing was conducted according to Stage 2 of the proposed framework. In this context, after experimentation, we determined that extracting 200 frames evenly distributed throughout the entire captured video, was the optimal choice to achieve a satisfactory balance among frames overlap and dataset size. Samples

Fig. 3: UAV image samples from the custom-built dataset, illustrating the examined construction from different viewing angles.

Fig. 4: Results of the automatic semantic annotation of collected RGB images. With light red color is illustrated the detected pillar instance, while background is colored with black.

of the extracted frames can be seen in Figure 3, which depict the bridge pillar from different viewing angles.

Next, to feed the semantic-NeRF model with 2D semantic labels and end up with a 3D annotated model, pixel labeling of each extracted image was automatically performed using a segmentation model. More specifically, the 200 RGB images were fed to the deployed DeepLabv3+ model, classifying pixels belonging to pillar as "column" and all the other pixels as "background". Through this process, we acquired the semantic pixel-level labels of the collected data. Results of the labeling process are demonstrated in Figure 4.

In the final step of Stage 2, camera poses were estimated for the extracted 200 RGB images following the aforementioned process. To achieve that, we utilized Hierarchical Localization (HLOC) [26] toolbox exploiting the SuperPoint and SuperGlue pretrained models for feature extraction and feature matching,

Fig. 5: Results of the camera poses estimation for the custom-built dataset. (a) different viewing angles of the estimated camera poses visualized via nerfstudio [29]. Each image’s estimated capture location is represented in 3D space. (b) UAV trajectory based on estimated capture positions

respectively. For the triangulation process based on the acquired features and the iterative optimization, we employed COLMAP [28] tool, leading to the estimated intrinsic camera parameters and the camera poses for the collected images. In Figure 5, the estimated camera poses in 3D space are demonstrated.

Once the data preprocessing of Stage 2 was completed, the derived custom-built dataset was utilized to train the Semantic-NeRF model for the specific scene. To this end, the 200 aerial images along with the generated semantic labels and the camera poses were fed to the deployed Semantic-NeRF model. Following the configuration in [38], the training images were resized to 320×240 . The model was trained for $200k$ steps, with Adam optimizer and learning rate equal to $5e^{-4}$. The overall process was conducted in a GeForce RTX 3090 GPU with 24GB memory.

The semantic 3D reconstruction of the pillar was acquired from the trained model, based on the methodology presented in section 3.3. Figure 6 presents different viewing angles of the acquired 3D representation. One can notice that the examined pillar instance is efficiently reconstructed and clearly distinguishable from the background class. Details regarding the shape and the surface recesses of the captured pillar are highly visible in the extracted 3D reconstruction. Some noisy patterns are also depicted in the background area. This effect is generated due to the nature of the background, which contains several instances in various scales and sizes that are not captured as detailed as the pillar instance during the UAV mission. These elements are not considered as of equal importance, and thus, are not adequately reconstructed. Overall, the acquired 3D representation is a valuable asset, enclosing in detail the geometry of the scene and containing high-level semantic information that can be valuable for downstream construction monitoring tasks.

Fig. 6: Different viewing angles of the semantic 3D representation of the examined construction area. With orange color is depicted the pillar instance, while background information is colored with green.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we propose an innovative framework that combines the economy and speed of UAV imagery acquisition with the capabilities of semantic NeRF to facilitate the creation of detailed 3D models of construction sites.

Our experiments, which focused particularly on a highway bridge construction site, highlighted the possibility of autonomously creating 3D models with texture and semantic classifications directly from raw UAV visual data. This not only serves as an important step towards creating valuable digital twin representations of the as-built condition, enhancing various monitoring and construction management applications, but also marks a shift away from the limitations of traditional point clouds, adding semantic depth to reconstructed objects.

Despite the promising results, the approach has a few notable limitations. The need for data preprocessing introduces an additional step before the actual analysis can begin. Also, the data labeling process is not entirely foolproof, posing a risk of potential mislabels that might compromise the results. Another constraint, inherent to the case-specific training requirements of semantic NeRFs, is the necessity to deploy the entire training process for each individual scene. These challenges highlight critical areas requiring further improvement and development to enhance both the efficiency and reliability of the system in future iterations. Furthermore, the paper acknowledges the need for further validation to establish the quantitative accuracy of the generated models. In our work, we mainly focused on demonstrating the integration of various technologies into an end-to-end framework for real-case scenarios in the construction industry. Looking ahead, we aim to broaden the scope of our research by incorporating a more diverse range of semantic classes relevant to construction, further optimizing each stage of the pipeline, and extending our experiments to

a wider variety of construction sites, including comprehensive evaluation metrics and comparative analyses. This, we believe, will make a significant contribution to the growing field of digitalization of construction applications, offering a low-cost and automated approach to transferring as-built conditions to digital twins or XR applications.

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